

Assessment of Indigenously Developed ^{99m}Tc -DTPA Bis-Methionine (^{99m}Tc -MDM) Qualitatively and Quantitatively During Initial Clinical Assessment in Breast Cancer Patients

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More Information

How to cite this article: Negi M, Dhingra VK, Narayan ML, Chowdhury N, Hazari PP, Mishra AK, Syed K. Assessment of Indigenously Developed ^{99m}Tc -DTPA Bis-Methionine (^{99m}Tc -MDM) Qualitatively and Quantitatively During Initial Clinical Assessment in Breast Cancer Patients. Eur J Med Health Res, 2025;3(3):65-9.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2025.3(3).09

Keywords:

Radiopharmaceutical,
MDM kit,
Gamma Camera,
99Mo ^{99m}Tc Generator.

Abstract

Introduction: Radionuclide-based tracers for SPECT and PET imaging have proven useful in the early detection of breast cancer. While C-11 methionine is an established PET tracer, its high cost and limited availability restrict its widespread clinical use. In contrast, ^{99m}Tc -MDM demonstrates promise as an alternative, with uptake facilitated by the overexpression of amino acid transporters, particularly via the LAT1 transporter in tumour cells. It is cost-effective and readily available, making it a potential candidate for identifying malignant breast lesions. Prior to administration, ensuring radiopharmaceutical quality through rigorous quality control is essential to uphold imaging standards in nuclear medicine. **Aim:** To evaluate both qualitatively and quantitatively the indigenously developed ^{99m}Tc -MDM (DTPA-bis-methionine) during its early clinical application in patients presenting with breast lesions. **Objectives:** To assess the physiological uptake pattern of ^{99m}Tc -MDM in patients with breast cancer; To determine the radiolabelling efficiency of the indigenously formulated ^{99m}Tc -MDM kits. **Results:** Physiological uptake of ^{99m}Tc -MDM was observed in the kidneys (51/51 patients), liver (50/51), gallbladder (12/51), and bowel (21/51). Quantitative analysis indicated a radiochemical purity of approximately 95%. **Conclusion:** The indigenously produced ^{99m}Tc -MDM kits demonstrated high labelling efficiency (>95%) and consistent physiological biodistribution, primarily involving the kidneys, liver, gallbladder, and bowel. Normal breast tissue in pre-menopausal women exhibited moderate and homogenous tracer uptake, whereas post-menopausal women showed mild and homogenous uptake. These findings suggest that ^{99m}Tc -MDM may serve as a viable, cost-effective imaging agent for the evaluation of breast lesions.

Introduction

Radiopharmaceuticals are crucial to nuclear medicine imaging, which creates images of interior bodily

functions that target particular organs, tissues, or physiological processes by combining a radioactive isotope with a pharmaceutical. Quality control of

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Radiopharmaceuticals is one of the key factors in evaluating the overall quality performance of nuclear medicine imaging. It highlights the tracer's assurance whether or not it is given to the patient. It verifies the purity of the radiopharmaceutical and radionuclide to ensure that no risks will arise [1,9]. Maintaining the tracer's potency, purity, and safety is its key goal. Its objective is to maintain the tracer' potency, purity, and safety. To administer radiopharmaceuticals to patients without any risk, it is crucial to verify physical, physiochemical, and biological testing before radiopharmaceutical administration. Maintaining a sterile environment throughout the radiopharmaceutical preparation time is an important step in radiopharmaceutical quality assurance which is maintained by laminar air flow [2].

Different SPECT and PET agents are used for imaging the breast cancer: ^{99m}Tc -HEDP, ^{99m}Tc -MDP, ^{99m}Tc -MDM, ^{99m}Tc -RGD, ^{99m}Tc - FES, ^{99m}Tc -Folate are SPECT agents and ^{18}F -FDG, ^{18}F -FLT, ^{18}F -FET, ^{68}Ga -RGD, ^{68}Ga FAPI, ^{18}F -4FMFES, ^{18}F -FFNP, ^{89}Zr -trastuzumab, ^{64}Cu -DOTA-trastuzumab, ^{89}Zr -pertuzumab are PET agents [3]. But ^{99m}Tc -MDM, ^{99m}Tc - FES, ^{18}F -FDG and ^{18}F -FLT are the tumor-seeking agents that detect the primary breast lesions [4].

Researchers have developed radiolabeled amino acids for tumor imaging using imaging techniques such as [^{18}F]F-DOPA, [^{18}F]F-FET, and [^{11}C]MET. These radiopharmaceuticals are taken up by cancer cells that are associated with LAT1 system for amino acid transport. The transport of amino acid is a bidirectional exchange mechanism across both sides of the endothelial cells which can reduce sensitivity compared to the entrapment mechanism in ^{18}F -FDG [5]. However, the advantage of using amino acids with SPECT radioisotope for tumor imaging is that these are easily labeled, easily available, and have indigenous preparation. Therefore, there is a need to evaluate a tracer [^{99m}Tc - MDM (DTPA Bis-methionine)] qualitatively and quantitatively [6].

Aim of the study

To assess qualitatively and quantitatively indigenously prepared ^{99m}Tc - MDM (DTPA Bis-methionine) during early clinical assessment in patients with breast lesions.

Study Objectives

- To qualitatively assess the physiological uptake of ^{99m}Tc -MDM in patients presenting with breast lesions.
- To quantitatively evaluate the labelling efficiency of the indigenously prepared ^{99m}Tc -MDM kits.

Materials and Methods

Equipment:

- Dual head SPECT/CT- NM CT 670

Materials Required

- ^{99}Mo - ^{99m}Tc Generator

- Scintimammography pads
- MDM kit- Supplied by Division of Cyclotron & Radiopharmacy, Institute of Nuclear Medicine & Allied Sciences (INMAS), Delhi
- QC kit with whatmann paper 3 strips
- Well counter with standard source

Radiopharmaceutical used

^{99m}Tc - MDM (~ 15-20mCi) standard adult dose

Elution of ^{99}Mo - ^{99m}Tc Generator

Radioactivity was eluted using saline and a vacuum vial from ^{99}Mo - ^{99m}Tc Generator as Sodium Perchnetate ($^{99m}\text{TcO}_4^-$).

Preparation of Radiopharmaceutical

For the labelling of ^{99m}Tc -MDM, approximately 15–20 mCi of sodium pertechnetate was introduced into a vial designated for single-patient use. The total volume was adjusted to 1.5 mL using 0.9% sodium chloride (normal saline), followed by the withdrawal of an equal volume of air to maintain pressure balance. The contents were then mixed thoroughly and incubated for 15–20 minutes. Post-incubation, the labelled ^{99m}Tc -MDM solution was filtered through a 0.22 μm Millipore filter prior to administration. The radiopharmaceutical preparation was subsequently evaluated for both qualitative and quantitative parameters.

Procedure

For quality control of radiopharmaceutical, an acetone (0.5 ml) was withdrawn from a syringe and poured into the test tube. A whatmann strip III was taken and a drop of radiopharmaceutical was put on the strip. For checking the purity of radiopharmaceutical, ascending paper chromatography was performed. In this method, Whatman strip III served as a stationary phase, while acetone was used as a mobile phase (solvent). A drop of radiopharmaceutical was put on the Whatmann strip and the strip was put into the test tube and the solute was moved with solvent. Once the chromatography procedure was completed, the strip was removed from the test tube and allowed to dry. After drying, the strip was then cut into three equal parts and measured in a well counter. The radiochemical purity was calculated for 20 samples, and the biodistribution of the samples was studied during imaging. Radiochemical purity (RCP) was calculated in this way [9].

Figure 1: Paper Chromatography Procedure

Figure 2: Free & Bound Fraction of Radiopharmaceutical as Determined by the Paper Chromatography Procedure

$$\% \text{ Free fraction [A]} = \frac{A}{A+B+C} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

$$\% \text{ Radiochemical purity} = 100 - \% \text{ Free (A)} \quad (2)$$

For clinical studies, approx. 15-20mCi ^{99m}Tc-MDM was injected intravenously into the patients under a gamma camera.

Results

Qualitatively assessment of ^{99m}Tc MDM

Total of 55 patients with breast lesions were available for evaluation. The biodistribution image of this tracer was acquired in 51 patients. The labelling efficiency on the scans was found to be satisfactory in all patients. Physiological uptake of tracer ^{99m}Tc MDM was seen in the kidneys, liver, gallbladder and bowel across 51, 50, 12, and 21 out of 51 patients, respectively. The thyroid gland was visualized in 2 out of 55 patients which was due to poor radiolabelling of ^{99m}Tc MDM. Tc-^{99m} MDM did not show uptake in normal bone, brain and muscles. Physiological biodistribution of ^{99m}Tc MDM in various body organs shown on Figures 3-5.

Figure 3: Physiological Uptake of ^{99m}Tc MDM in Various Body Organs

Figure 4: Biodistribution of ^{99m}Tc MDM

Figure 5: Case Images: (I) Pre-Menopause Woman (age 35 years) & (II) Post-Menopausal Woman (age 56 years)

Moderate, homogenous breast uptake was observed in normal breast in pre-menopausal woman while mild, homogenous breast uptake was observed in post-menopausal woman.

Quantitatively measurement of ^{99m}Tc MDM (radiolabeling efficiency %)

The radiochemical purity of ^{99m}Tc- MDM was calculated ~95% with total 20 number of samples as shown in a graph (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Graph between the % age of bound fraction of ^{99m}Tc MDM & number of samples

Discussion

In previous studies, different SPECT and PET radiotracers like F-18 FDG, C-11 L- MET and F-18 FET have been documented for breast cancer imaging, however they are expensive and give additional radiation burden to the patients. 11C- Methionine is used as an alternative tumor agent as compared to 18F-FDG as it only localizes in tumor cell but 18F FDG localizes in both tumor as well as inflammatory site. C-11 L-Methionine (L-MET) has limited use in routine clinical practice primarily due to its half-life (t1/2 = 20 minutes) and the requirement for an in-house cyclotron facility. Its physiological uptake was seen in bone marrow, low uptake in brain (in glioma) and no uptake was visualized in muscles. In contrast, 99mTc-MDM was explored in this study, offering several potential advantages. These include the ability for indigenous preparation, reduced radiation burden (with 6 hours half-life and energy 140 keV), and easier availability. The uptake mechanisms of both C-11 L-MET and 99mTc-MDM are similar, primarily involving the LAT1 (L-type amino acid transporter 1) receptor [7]. The physiological uptake of ^{99m}Tc MDM was seen in liver, gallbladder, kidney and bowel and no uptake was seen in in brain, muscle and bone.

In preclinical studies mainly in mice, the biodistribution of the tracer was assessed qualitatively and also quantify the localization of the radiolabeled tracer on U-87MG, BMG, and EAT tumors grafted in mice [10]. The biodistribution of ^{99m}Tc MDM was seen in kidneys, gall bladder, liver and bowel [11]. The U-87MG & BMG cell line implanted in mice was shown uptake in kidneys. In this study, the biodistribution of ^{99m}Tc

Methionine and ^{99m}Tc MDM was revealed in mice bearing with EAT tumors. A Comparative analysis of ^{99m}Tc Methionine and ^{99m}Tc MDM in EAT tumor-bearing mice indicated that ^{99m}Tc Methionine was primarily localized in the liver but ^{99m}Tc MDM demonstrated reduced hepatic uptake and lower accumulation in the stomach and small intestine.[6]

In earlier clinical studies, the fast clearance from renal was observed in human volunteers. Two hours dose post-administration, the tracer was predominantly excreted via the kidneys, with physiological uptake observed in the liver. [6,8]

In our study, the biodistribution of this tracer was assessed by acquiring whole body scintigraphy at 10min or 60min. The whole body image was acquired for all patients which showed physiological uptake in kidney, liver, gall bladder & bowel. This was similar to the observed distribution seen in other studies [6, 7, 8]. The physiological uptake of tracer was seen in the kidneys, liver, and gallbladder and bowel across 51, 50, 12 and 21 out of 51 patients, respectively. The thyroid gland was seen in 2 out of 55 patients which is due to some technical error in the preparation of radiopharmaceutical. This data showed that 53/55 (96.3%) samples were satisfactory radiolabelled.

Conclusion

Indigenously produced ^{99m}Tc-MDM kits were found to be robust, with radiolabelling efficiency of ^{99m}Tc- MDM was nearly ~95% which was in the acceptable range and the physiological tracer uptake was visualized in kidneys, gall bladder, liver, and bowel. The biodistribution was found to be satisfactory in all patients. Moderate, homogenous breast uptake was

observed in normal breast in pre-menopausal women while mild, homogenous breast uptake was observed in post-menopausal women. Tc-^{99m} MDM did not show uptake in normal bone, brain and muscles.

Acknowledgement

Professor Meenu Singh, Executive Director and CEO, AIIMS Rishikesh & Dr. Sudhir Chandna, Distinguished & Director, INMAS, Delhi for facilitating this work.

Conflict of Interest

None

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